

GEOGRAPHICAL CONDITIONS AND CULTURAL TRADITION AS DETERMINANTS IN SUSTAINING TOURISM VILLAGE PROGRAM

CASE STUDY TOURISM VILLAGES IN YOGYAKARTA

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Abstract

Ecotourism, as a part of sustainable tourism, has been growing rapidly in Indonesia in many rural areas in Yogyakarta. This is because mass tourism changed the emphasis onto nature and cultural tourism so that rural tourism became interesting to tourists. This paper aims to study the development of rural tourism in Yogyakarta in terms of mileage, geographical conditions, period of growth and tourist attractions. Descriptive analysis is used to identify the influence factors based on distribution of location, historical factors, and cultural and geographical conditions in tourism villages in Yogyakarta. Rural tourism in Yogyakarta has been growing since the year 2000. The dominant attraction is related to cultural tourism based on community participation. Research results show that geographic condition and local cultural tradition, which support the traditional daily income of the local community, became the determinant factors in sustaining the touristic village of Yogyakarta.

1. Introduction

Yogyakarta as a tourist destination has a uniqueness that attract tourists both domestic and foreign. Along with the development of the tourism industry, tourist interest began to change from a mass tourism destination to a tourist destination with a small group that prioritizes experience. Ecotourism and special interest is a "trend" that need to be observed. (Fandeli, 2000). An open country that prioritizes sustainable tourism is interesting for today's travelers. (ITB, 2016). Ecotourism is a relatively new tourism trend in Indonesia, although internationally since October 1999 the World Tourism Organization has actually issued "Global Code of Ethics for Tourism" as encouragement to the countries of the world to develop sustainable tourism. (UNWTO, GLOBAL CODE OF ETHICS FOR TOURISM, 2001)

As an extension of alternative tourism, ecotourism has evolved as a consequence of dissatisfaction with conventional forms of tourism in general, ignoring social and ecological elements, which favor anthropocentricity, as well as making a more centralized profit approach to offering tourist products. (Fennell, 2008). Form of ecotourism-based tourism and cultural activities began to appear in Yogyakarta. Currently, there are 81 tourism villages in Yogyakarta province have been developed. (DISPARBUD-Sleman, 2012); (DISPARBUD-Bantul, 2013); (DISPARBUD-Gunungkidul., 2014); (DISPARBUD-Kulonprogo, 2014). Village tourism program launched by the Indonesian government through the Tourism Department in 2005 which was followed up by government regulations through the implementation of National Program for Community Empowerment (called "PNPM Mandiri) in 2008, has significantly increased the number of tourism villages in Indonesia. (Hadiwijoyo, 2012). The development of agrarian-based village into a tourism village is an interesting phenomenon that needs to be studied continuously. Theoretically this "trend" is a positive phenomenon as a feature of sustainable environment. This paper aims to examine the potential tourist attractions of tourism villages sustainability in

Yogyakarta. This identification is beneficial for future development established by the government to determine the direction of regional-based development policies.

2. Method

Research conducted to get the study of the distribution of this tourist village use explorative paradigm by using relationship analysis between the factors supporting the sustainability of the tourist village with existing condition in Yogyakarta province. Generally, this research attempts to clarify the relationship pattern between 2 or more variables with reality condition. (Groat & Wang, 2013). The analysis process is done by using secondary data archive analysis to know what, who and how many. (Yin, 2003). This method is chosen because it focuses on the contextual context of the present. The supporting factors of the sustainability of the tourist village are taken based on the requirements of the tourism village, i.e : accessibility, attractions, community, security, accommodation, climate and networking. (DIPARTA-DIY, 2014); (Priasukmana & Mulyadin, 2001). Measurement of distribution to take aspect of time of establishment of tourist village which is associated with the declaration of village tourism programs by the government, so this study can examine what influences the sustainability of tourist villages in 4 districts based on the time of its establishment. Schematically, the flow of discussion of this paper can be seen through the chart in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1. Research Schematic (author, 2017)

3. Overview of Tourism Village in Yogyakarta

Village tourism program in Yogyakarta emerged as a response to the establishment of the Community Based Tourism program proclaimed by the Indonesian government, But the concept of rural tourism has begun to be developed since 1998 by Sri Sultan Hamengku Buwono X as the governor of Yogyakarta who also domiciled as the king of the Sultan's Palace. Yogyakarta as a special region has unique characteristics that distinguish with other provinces in Indonesia. The customary position of the king can affect daily life of local community in Yogyakarta. King as the traditional leader as well as the governor as the administrative leader of the government cause relationship the leaders and people of Yogyakarta become intimately. Given the long history of the Yogyakarta Palace which was founded in 1755, the existence of Kraton Yogyakarta can not be separated from buffer zone in the form of rural area which holds many roles such as agricultural production centers and crops, security of the region to the spread of religion. (Abimanyu, 2015). The village became the backbone of the Yogyakarta's agrarian tradition. Kraton Yogyakarta attention to rural development cause rural tourism become an alternative income society as well as a means of preserving the natural environment of rural areas, both physically and non-physically in the form of daily tradition. The condition behind the emergence of the concept of rural tourism in Yogyakarta cause priority of the development of tourism villages in Yogyakarta more directed to the tradition-based tourist village, both daily and cultural artifacts.

Ecotourism rests on rural tourism, nature tourism and cultural tourism. (Nugroho, 2011). Theoretically this "trend" is a positive phenomenon if seen as a feature of a sustainable environment. Villages are being treated to remain a beautiful village to reduce the villagers' willingness to sell land that gradually becomes new settlement land and reduce fertile land. One of the efforts that can be done to protect rice fields in the suburbs is by developing creative industries, namely sustainable tourism. In line with this, World Tourism Organization defines sustainable tourism development as a development that meets the needs of today's travelers, while protecting and encouraging opportunities for the foreseeable future. (UNWTO, GLOBAL CODE OF ETHICS FOR TOURISM, 2001)

The development of tourism village in Yogyakarta can't be separated from rural development in general. Rural development is an effort to improve and equalize the economy, especially in rural areas. Rural areas are transformed as a result of village development. The transformation can't be directed to the evolution of agricultural villages into industrial villages and then into trade villages, but every type of village development can build together. (Agusta, 2014). Connected with the development of the tourism sector, in particular the transformation can lead to cultural transition such as the transition of society and agrarian culture to industrial culture (tourism) and transition of a closed society into an open society with a global culture. (Setyadi, 2007). Two forms of transition are more dominant in the villages that become tourist destinations. The development of traditional and cultural-based tourist villages is an effort to prevent the change of local values in rural communities in Yogyakarta. In line with that opinion, locations that are supported by physical potential with local culture can be a driver and controller of the development of tourist villages. (Pudianti, 2012). Tourism development attraction i.e. cultural tradition attraction, nature, a blend of cultural and natural traditions and local crafts in line with period of the establishment of tourist village. They can be supporting factor for the development of tourism villages which can identify the sustainability of tourist villages in Yogyakarta. Identification of the distribution of the number of tourism villages in Yogyakarta according to tourist attractions in each district can be described by the graph in Figure 3 below.

Figure 3. Graph of distribution number of tourist villages based on the potential tourist attraction in 4 districts of DIY province (author, 2017)

Based on the data it can be seen that the year of declaration of the village tourism program as part of the central government program of the Republic of Indonesia in 2005 increased the number of tourist villages sharply (see table 1). Based on these data, Bantul and Sleman become the districts with the most tourism villages. The tourist attraction is dominated by traditional and natural attractions for Sleman district. While the attractions of handicrafts and the combination of nature and tradition dominate the tourism village in Bantul district (see Figure 3 on Bantul and Sleman Graph). The growing attractions in Sleman district are in line with local livelihood conditions which is in the agricultural sector. The geographical condition of Sleman district located on the slopes of Merapi volcano makes its area fertile for agriculture since the era of Mataram kingdom. (BPS-Kab.Sleman, 2016). The dominance of livelihoods makes agricultural traditions a distinctive cultural feature developed for tourist villages. Bantul district, located in the southern part of Yogyakarta province, is dominated by livelihood community from trading and handicraft industry. (BPS-Kab.Bantul, 2016). Character of coastal communities in accordance with the landscape approaching the southern coastal region resulted in craft and trade can grow well.

The role of geographical physical condition and cultural tradition as an attraction that dominates the development of tourist village can be seen through the identification table of the growth of tourist villages based on the year of establishment and tourist attraction in Yogyakarta in table 1 below.

Table 1. Identification of tourism village growth in Yogyakarta base on year of establishment

Year of establishment	Tradition	Nature	Nature and tradition	Local handicraft	Summary
Before 2005	3	8	1	2	14
After 2005	16	26	12	13	67
Summary	19	34	13	15	81

Source : Author, 2017

The identification of dominant tourist attractions shows that the tourist attractions that drive the tourism village are the geographical physical conditions that are visible through the natural attractions (see Table 1 column 3). Geographical physical condition in the form of natural tourism attractions consistently become the trigger of the

development of tourism villages. Both before the era of declaration of programs in 2005 and after the era of declaration program after 2005. While the cultural tradition as a tourist attraction to be a second driver (see table 1 column 2). Further seen in column 4, the physical geographic mix in the form of natural attractions and cultural attractions can be a potential for tourism village development. So it can be concluded that the two things are decisive in the development of programs that can affect the sustainability of tourism villages in Yogyakarta until today.

5. Geographical Physical Condition and Cultural Tradition in sustaining tourism village program

Geographical physical condition and cultural tradition is a tourist attraction that becomes attraction for tourists to visit. The uniqueness of the geographical physical condition and cultural traditions of a village become important in the development of tourism villages, especially in the province of Yogyakarta. Sustainability of tourist villages, both as a concept of community empowerment to develop the village as well as the response of rural tourism program, can be identified by looking at the potential of tourist attraction.

5.1. Development of Tourism Village in Yogyakarta before the declaration of village tourism program

In the era before the declaration of village tourism program, tourism villages grow by rely on natural attraction as happened in Ketingan tourism village in Sleman district and Nglinggo tourism village in Kulonprogo district. Both of these tourism villages rely on natural attractions such as bird watching in Ketingan and tea plantations in Nglinggo. Ketingan tourist village was inaugurated in 2000. Bird watching becomes a tourist attraction because of its location is one of the stopover location of the heron bird, especially in the rainy season to breed. Geographical conditions of beautiful Ketingan village, with farms and shady trees are suitable for breeding habitat. The uniqueness of this nature becomes the attraction for tourists, especially bird lovers to observe the natural habitats of birds that blend with rural atmosphere. (see figure 4a). While Nglinggo tourism village which was inaugurated in 2004 rely on tourist attractions in the form of tea plantations managed by PT Pagilaran. Its geographical location at an altitude of 900 - 1000 m asl make this location suitable for tea plantations. (see figure 5b). Its history as one of former place used by prince Diponegoro in the fight against Dutch colonial is value-added to the tourist attraction of this village.

Figure 4(a) Tourist attraction in Ketingan (Kurniawan, 2012) Figure 5(b) Tourist attraction in Nglinggo (Bernadi, 2015)

Beside tourist attractions that rely on geographical physical condition, tourism villages in Yogyakarta also rely on tradition and culture as a tourist attraction. The existence of cultural tradition became the forerunner of the concept of rural tourism-based village development initiated by Sri Sultan Hamengku Buwono X in 1999 at the East Asian Tourism Forum (EATOF) program in Brayut village. (Utomo, 2017). The concept of rural tourism is emerging because the village as a buffer zone of the city needs an alternative way to improve its development. Authenticity agrarian-based cultural traditions by rely on the physical conditions of geographic become an attraction offered to tourists. Villages that have a homogeneous character cause the influence of modernization does not affect the daily lives of citizens. Brayut tourism village and Tembi tourism village emerged as model of cultural-based tourist village. Brayut tourism village in Sleman district was inaugurated in 1999, has the attractiveness of a variety of traditional Javanese dwelling architecture that shows the high level of socio-economic level of this villagers in the past. Traditional Javanese house located in Brayut still occupied by the owner and his descendants to this day, so the condition is well maintained (see figure 6c). Entering the tourist village Brayut, like entering the laboratory architecture of a traditional living house. This uniqueness becomes an attraction for tourists. Meanwhile, Tembi tourism village in Bantul regency was inaugurated in 1997, rely on the tourist attraction of Java rural atmosphere. The beautiful atmosphere supported by the tradition of mendong crafts (made of pandanus plants) combined with the agriculture cause Tembi became one of the destinations of foreign tourists who come to Yogyakarta. (see figure 7d).

c.

d.

Figure 6(c) Tourist Attraction in Brayut (author, 2017) Figure 7(d) Tourist attraction in Tembi (author, 2017)

5.2. Development of a tourism village in Yogyakarta after the declaration of a village tourism program

Distance not being considered as long as the tourist landscape is unique in attracting tourists as in the example of Pentingsari village in Sleman established in 2007 (see figure 8a). This village relies on the authenticity of mountain village atmosphere although located approximately 25 km from downtown Yogyakarta. Similarly, some special interest tourism villages such as Nglanggeran tourism village in Gunungkidul which was inaugurated in 2006. This village relies on tourist attraction of ancient volcanoes (see figure 10c), is 26 km from downtown Yogyakarta. As well as Kalibiru tourism village in Kulonprogo which was established in 2008. This village relies on the attraction of protected forests and views of the reservoir sermo. (see figure 9b) within 35 km from Yogyakarta city center.

a.

b.

Figure 8(a) rural atmosphere in Pentingsari (author, 2017) Figure 9(b) landscape in Kalibiru (author, 2017)

c.

Figure 10(c) landscape in Nglanggeran (projst02, 2013)

Village tours that rely on special interest tourism in the form of landscape objects are able to attract tourists in large numbers but if not managed well in the long term, it can experience depreciation both the physical environment and the interests of tourists. Sustainable management is important for tourism village managers. Innovation and creativity are supporting factors for the sustainability of tourist villages based on geographical physical condition. Responses can be creating a variety of attractions that involve tourists actively such as the development of outbound activities and educational tours. The example of the village Pentingsari, natural atmosphere combined with village tourism activities by involving tourists to plow the fields, fishing, and stringing *janur* (decoration made from young coconut leaf) as a decoration for traditional ceremonies. (see figure 11a and 12b).

a.

b.

Figure 11(a) Fishing attraction in Pentingsari (author, 2017) Figure 12(b) “menjanur” attraction in Pentingsari (author, 2017)

While in the tourist village of Kalibiru and Nglingo, the manager developed a tour package spot panoramic photo and educational tour of tea plantation. (see figure 13c and 14d).

c.

b.

Figure 13c. Photospot in Kalibiru (author, 2016)

Figure 14d. Teawalk in Nglingo (Bernadi, 2015)

Villagers's daily cultural traditions including crafts and cultural artifacts become an interesting tourist attraction, considering Yogyakarta is known as a cultural city. Tradition is more potential to invite tourists back to visit because of the emotional involvement with the local community in the tourist village.

a.

b.

Figure 15(a) traditional house in Brayut (author, 2017)

Figure 16b. Mendong handicraft in Tembi (author, 2017)

For example in Bantul district, developing tourist villages rely on traditional handicrafts such as woven mendong (from pandan leaf) in Tembi tourist village (see figure 16b), traditional cuisine in Lopati tourism village (see figure 17c), and pottery handicrafts in Kasongan tourism village (see figure 18d). Tourists can interact with villagers in the craft industry. Traditional craftsmanship using local raw materials is an attraction for tourists. Cultural artifacts as a product of the traditional built environment in the tourism village is also an attraction for tourists Such as a rural environment with traditional house architecture in the tourist village of Brayut district of Sleman. (see figure 15a).

c.

d.

Figure 17c. bamboo basket in Lopati (Ipank, 2012)

Figure 18d. Pottery handicraft in Kasongan (Farhan, 2012)

The trend of the development of tourist interest is behind the development of village tourism program so that leads to nature tourism that blends with cultural traditions. In table 1, can be seen that typology of rural tourism that relies on the combination of nature and tradition become more developed after declaration of the program. In other words, geographical physical conditions, cultural traditions and the combination of the two became the determinant of the sustainability of the tourist village in Yogyakarta. To maintain the sustainability, tourism villages need human resources as a driving attraction. Good management by rural communities can result in sustained improvements in the economy.

6. Community participation as a driver in the development of tourism village

The development of tourist villages to improve the welfare of rural communities needs to be accompanied by efforts to empower the village community mainly related to the knowledge of sustainable tourism. Community-based sustainable cultural tourism involves tangible utilization and intangible cultural resources to support the cultural, social and economic vitality of local communities, creating understanding among stakeholders, making it easier to provide authentic and interesting experiences for visitors. (UNWTO, Tourism and Culture Partnership in Peru – Models for Collaboration, 2016). The empowerment process undertaken by the community is expected to be the responsibility of the community itself. Local community can have the ability to make decisions and carry out all decisions individually or in groups, in utilizing local resources to improve their welfare. (Sutawa, 2012). The key to the development of tourist villages is the participation of villagers in the village. Community participation in rural areas of Yogyakarta is quite good considering the tradition of “gotong royong” a mutual cooperation that is still attached to the daily lives of citizens. Javanese culture of mutual respect and “tepa selira” (understanding each other) resulted in reliable community participation. On the other hand the typical character of the village community such as the desire to move forward, competing and achieving success can be a motivation for the community to develop their village As happened in Pentingsari tourism village district of Sleman. Despite being located in an isolated access area, but the strong desire of Pentingsari villagers can prove to be the best tourism village. (Vitasurya, 2016).

7. Conclusions

The sustainability of the tourist village in Yogyakarta is dominated by the factors that become the determinants :

- Geographical physical condition, the beauty and authenticity of the preserved landscape becomes an attraction if it has a unique uniqueness like Pentingsari, Kalibiru, Nglanggeran but need to be added with the uniqueness that touches the emotions of visitors to return. In the era after the declaration of village tourism program, geographical physical condition with the natural tourist attraction develops when there is activity to attract visitors.
- Tradition of local culture, the uniqueness of tradition in the daily life of the community is an attraction for tourists. The uniqueness that touches the emotions will bring longing to return.

Geographical and local physical conditions become dominant in the sustainability of tourist villages in Yogyakarta. But it can move with the support of community participation. Based on the above analysis can be concluded that the two factors are mutually influence to maintain the sustainability of tourist villages in Yogyakarta.

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